

Towards a software pipeline for seamless robot-to-human handover

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Abstract—This work presents a modular software architecture for robotic handover. The architecture includes: neuromorphic perception for detection and estimation of human movements; motion predictors for anticipating partners movements and adapt to them; and finally, adaptation mechanisms that command a low-level controller for a robotic arm equipped with an anthropomorphic hand, for object seamless motion and release. Preliminary results in robot-to-human handover involving the modules of prediction and low-level control corroborate the effectiveness of the proposed architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective Human-Robot Cooperation (HRC) depends on the ability to achieve seamless object handovers, a skill deeply ingrained in human interactions. Humans excel at perceiving partner actions, adapting in real-time, and exchanging objects fluidly [1][2]. Replicating this proficiency in robots demands intricate perceptual, planning, and control mechanisms. In this work we propose a software architecture that enables handover behavior in a robotic platform.

The robotic handover task presents significant challenges. One of the major challenges is to make the robot socially aware of the human presence, intentionality and behaviour. Traditional vision system requires extremely complex algorithms to achieve such social awareness. One promising technology is the neuromorphic vision performed with event-based cameras. Event-cameras output data only when a change in the scene occurs, which is monitored individually for each pixel. The inherently compressed and asynchronous output results in smaller packets of data sent at a high temporal resolution. This property makes the cameras ideal for visual sensing of small and subtly gestures which require reactive response from robots. Such insights on human

movement are precious information necessary to infer the goals and the other details (e.g.: intentionality and style) of human actions. In the proposed software architecture, the neuromorphic perception and social interaction manager (SIM) module are driven by event-cameras to achieve low-latency and precise estimation of the complex and subtle motions that occur in hand-over tasks. It is SIM objective to interpret the raw data about the movement and predict how human action evolves.

The anticipation of the outcomes of an action is fundamental when the online adaptation is not sufficient to accomplish the joint activities. Consequently, seamless handover requires anticipation and prediction of the partner's movement to achieve successful collaboration. By taking the cues in the human hand motion, robotic system could be endowed with capabilities which allow for online adaptation during the execution. Furthermore, this reactive behaviour is imperative in practical applications where the interaction could be susceptible to perturbations or interruptions. Additionally, to ensure smooth object exchange, the release strategy needs to allow for immediate collision detection. To achieve these capabilities, a Human Hand Predictor module is implemented in the proposed architecture to predict human hand motion and, from it, estimate the engagement in the handover. These predictions are then used by the LOW-level Control Engine Module (LOCEM) to generate and modulate online minimum-jerk trajectories, execute them, and eventually detect the collision using the Wrist Proprioceptive Filter and complete the interaction.

This paper delves into the complexities of realizing advanced robotic handovers within the context of practical HRC. Thus, we propose a modular software architecture for seamless robot-to-human handovers.

II. OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

The robot-to-human handover architecture is shown in Fig. 1. The kinematics and the prediction of the human motion are

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Fig. 1 Block diagram of the software architecture and the hardware components.

computed within the SIM starting from an asynchronous stream of events generated by a neuromorphic camera.

The information is sent to LOCEM which controls the motion of the robot arm and hand to produce a seamless handover. This pipeline is composed of different high level and low-level modules typically implemented either as a ROS Node or ROS Action Server. As shown in Fig. 1, some of these modules are nested: in this case the external module is responsible for the coordination of the internal ones and provides a more abstract and convenient interface for the execution of some typical actions.

The following sections provide an overview of the main modules.

III. NEUROMORPHIC PERCEPTION AND THE SOCIAL INTERACTION MANAGER – SIM

We use the neuromorphic cameras ATIS GEN3 to produce high-frequency state updates, and to generate accurate and smooth position and velocity estimates, compared to traditional visual sensors. The cameras offer millisecond latency, to drive immediate reactions from the safety system. The neuromorphic architecture for sensing and detecting intention of human actions is focused on the tracking of the end-effectors of the human operator and extracting velocity profiles, towards understanding intention and predicting behaviours of the operator. The system fuses measurements of end-effector position (from HPE) and velocity (using state-of-the-art event-based velocity estimation algorithms) to give a high-frequency (> 1 kHz) output of the end-effector position and velocity.

SIM is the core package for the interaction with the human worker. We describe a few of nodes that are developed in order to promote dependable interpretation of the human behaviour, and consequently to adapt the behaviour of the robot towards improved coordination with the worker during the handover task. In particular, the Human Hand Predictor, fundamental component in the SIM architecture, estimates the trajectory and the velocity of the human end effector in the time frame of a detected handover.

A. Human Pose Estimation (low frequency)

Human pose estimation is first performed to obtain a visual position of the end-effectors of the target. The detection of the full body of the target adds constraints to hand positions that reduces errors in position detection. Human pose estimation is performed using the MoveNet [3] algorithm; an event-driven adaptation of the MoveNet algorithm [4] for light-weight HPE. MoveNet requires events to be converted into a EROS [5] representation which can be queried at rates over 1000 kHz. With typical hardware (GPU) the MoveNet algorithm can generate human pose estimates at up to 100 Hz. However, to save computational resources and power the update rate of the detection algorithm can be lowered, and the system can rely more on velocity estimation of the hands.

B. Joint End-Effector Velocity Estimation (high frequency)

The position of the human hands are initialised from the human pose estimation algorithm. To give a high-frequency output of the hands, and accurate velocity profile, a velocity estimation algorithm is used. The event-driven algorithm takes advantage of the spatio-temporal data structures produced by the event-cameras for accurate velocity estimation, and the compressed data signal to integrate the velocities at a high-frequency (> 1 kHz). A modified triplet matching algorithm was designed to bring state-of-the-art event-driven velocity estimation algorithms to real-time applications. The modified algorithm performs matching over a data structure dubbed the "surface of active events". The algorithm complexity is modified to estimate velocity at as high a rate as possible, but is not performed for each and every event, which can lead to non-real-time computation. End-effector position and velocity is fused in a Kalman filter, in which the velocity is integrated over time to give an up-to-date estimate of the hand position with low latency.

C. Human Hand Predictor

To make short-term prediction of the position of the human hand and to estimate the engagement of the human partner a module based on two complementary Neural Networks (NN) is implemented. These two networks emulate

an anticipatory scheme of the handover execution. The first predictor, implemented as a LSTM architecture, is trained on general human hand motions, and predicts the short-term (~ 0.15 s) future trajectory of the human hand. The second network is trained on human-human handover trajectories and predicts the direction in which the human hand would move, should it be engaged in a handover. The mismatch of these two predictions is considered as a proxy for detecting whether the human is engaged in the handover and is passed to the Handover Speed Modulator to adjust the speed of robot trajectory. The less these two predictions are aligned, the less the confidence about the human hand motion matching a possible handover motion. An example of engagement detection, computed on a trajectory from past robot-human experiments, is shown in Fig. 2 as the scalar product between the two (normalized) predictions.

Fig. 2 Example of detection of engagement. The trajectory shown is the one of the human hand, involved in the perturbed task as presented in [6][6]. As such, the first part (A-B) is setup as to look like a handover motion. The second part (B-C) instead requires moving away from the interaction, and the final part (C-D) is when the human reaches for the object (handover). For more details about the experiment, the reader is referred to the original work. Here the predictors are applied to the recorded trajectories, and the scalar product is shown as a qualitative measure of alignment between the two predictions (future trajectory and handover direction) represented as unitary vectors.

IV. THE LOW-LEVEL CONTROL ENGINE MODULE – LOCEM

LOCEM decodes the high-level controls into simpler actions to instruct the robot to execute the grasp, as well as the movement of the arm avoiding collisions with the surrounding environments. In the robot-to-human handover, the LOCEM implements extra functionalities that can be used to perform a handover action (i.e., passing/receiving an object to/from a human partner). In this context we consider a robot-to-human handover, formed by two parts:

1. Estimation of the inertia of the object to be handed, with the scope of improved contact detection and performing a natural release;
2. Execution of a trajectory to approach the (receiving) human hand, with a modulation of the speed of this trajectory in response to the human’s hand motion.

The trajectory will be generated by the Online Trajectory Generator module, as a minimum-jerk tracking of the human hand. The execution of the trajectory will be performed by an Action Server, reading the predictions of the human hand and using them to set the target and to modulate the execution of the trajectory. The action server will then forward the

command from the generator to the Collision Aware Inverse Kinematic block.

A. Handover Speed Modulator

In a practical collaboration scenario, the handover could be susceptible to perturbations. The perturbations are considered as unmodeled disturbances on the trajectory of the receiver (e.g., external disturbances, receiver occupied with another task, or not engaging in the handover). As such, to generate robot trajectories, a pre-planned method would not suffice, and an online trajectory generation approach, based on a virtual dynamical system, is proposed. As introduced, such a system generates a minimum-jerk trajectory that converges to and track the human hand (Online Trajectory Generator). However, the speed of evolution of the whole dynamic system is scaled by the mismatch between the two predictors introduced in Sec. III.C. The mismatch is computed as the angle between the two predictions, and it is further processed to produce a value in $[0,1]$, with 1.0 leaving the system at full speed, and 0.0 completely stopping the system.

This processing is set up to 1) obtain a value of 0.0 for a mismatch above a certain (user-defined) threshold, stopping when the confidence in the handover engagement from the human is too low; 2) proceed at full speed when the mismatch is below a certain (user-defined) alignment, representing high-confidence in handover engagement; and 3) produce a smooth modulation of the speed between these two extremes. Furthermore, this system could interactively be tuned from direct human feedback to produce desired reactive behaviour intuitively [7].

B. Wrist Force Proprioceptive Filter

The Wrist Force Proprioceptive Filter is used to approximate the sensed payload at the robot wrist in terms of mass, center of mass, inertia tensor (the latter are expressed with respect to the wrist force/torque sensor measurement frame) [1]. Since the estimation process relies on the Newton-Euler’s equations of dynamics, this module can be also used to compensate force/torque information at the robot wrist which is solely given to the fact that the manipulator is carrying a payload. In the robot-to-human handover scenario, this means that the mild collision with the receiver’s hand (i.e., the human partner grasps the object to complete the handover) can be sensed at the robot wrist with maximum reactivity.

C. The Handover Release Controller

The Handover Release Controller relies on the output from the Wrist Force Proprioceptive Filter. In a robot-to-human handover scenario, the dynamics compensated wrench at the wrist level is used to detect the mild collision with the receiver’s hand (i.e., the beginning of the grasp action). On detection, the object must be released by the robotic giver which also relates the release time to the observed peak acceleration in the reaching dynamics of the human partner since this has been proved to increase the perceived fluency of the interaction [2].

D. Ancillary modules

The ancillary modules support the actions within the LOCEM, and are: the Mia Hand Commander, the Online Trajectory Generation, and the Collision Aware Inverse Kinematics modules.

The Mia Hand Commander is responsible for the execution of finger joint trajectories (e.g., from output of Grasp Refinement), each degree of freedom of the Mia Hand [8] (now commercialized by Prensilia Srl, model Mia Hand). This is actuated via a ROS standard PID position controller which relies on the joint velocity interface provided by the official hardware interface. The Mia Hand Commander provides a middle layer interface to forward a triplet of joint commands to the single PID controllers.

The Online Trajectory Generation generates Cartesian trajectories of the end-effector. A virtual dynamical system is implemented to generate smooth minimum-jerk trajectories. The trajectories are generated online, in a step-by-step fashion, allowing the virtual dynamical system to generate a trajectory that not only can reach a given static pose but also track a desired trajectory [6][7].

Finally, the Collision Aware Inverse Kinematics allows to online compute the collision free inverse kinematic of the robot. The algorithm is based on *CollisionIK* [9].

V. RESULTS

Fig. 3 Normalized speed profiles of human and hand and robot EE in handover scenario with a wrong starting command. Non-adaptive controller on the left, adaptive controller on the right.

Preliminary tests have been performed to validate the proposed architecture. In these tests, we did not use the Neuromorphic Perception and the SIM modules that were replaced by the output of a visual tracking system (VICON) for retrieving information about the partner movement. The task is a robot-to-human handover with perturbations. A perturbation that might arise in a practical scenario is some form of high-level control engaging the robot when the human is not ready to receive it. To emulate this, human demonstrators are charged with initiating a handover with auditory “Go” command slightly after the robot is already given the command to initiate the handover. Two controllers are considered. The first controller is non-reactive, thus it only uses Human Hand Predictors to predict the target for exchange and passes it to the Online Trajectory Generation module. The second controller (reactive) uses Human Hand Predictors fully, it estimates the human engagement in the handover and the target, adjusts accordingly via Handover Speed Modulator, and finally calls the Online Trajectory Generation module. From the speed profiles in Fig. 3 it can be observed that the non-reactive controller (left) initiates the movement before the human does, forcing the human to adapt to the robot motion. On the other hand, the reactive controller (right) does not move until human engagement is detected and adjusts accordingly.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents a modular software architecture for-robot-to-human handover. We presented the modules and provided results for an initial validation that include the Human-Hand Prediction module supported by the LOCEM in handover tasks. Next steps include the testing of the whole architecture, also including the SIM and the Neuromorphic Perception, in industrial environments.

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CONTRIBUTION

FR, AG and CB designed the early stages of the neuromorphic perception collecting and processing the events generated by the neuromorphic camera in order to estimate the velocity of the human hand during the handover action. MP and MContr designed and developed the Wrist Force Proprioceptive Filter, the Handover release controller, and the Mia Hand Commander. FI, GP, MConti, AM, EF, MContr designed and developed the Handover Speed Modulator, and the Human Hand Handover Prediction. EF, MContr supervised the activities.

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